

THE GREAT REPRESENTATIVE OF TURKISH MEDICINE OF THE 20TH CENTURY

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Abstract. *The article is about the life and work of Mominjon Hakim Margilani, medical activity, socio-political processes in the Khanate of Bukhara and Kokan Khanate in the early 20th century, education, theory and practice of medicine, exemplary aspects of the personality of Mominjon Hakim, Turkestan medicine, public health, population's attitude towards scientists. dedicated to the analysis of unique facts, the achievements of Mominjon Hakim in combining the advanced aspects of Eastern medicine and Western medicine, and the unique aspects of his unique personality.*

Keywords: *religious school, madrasah, theory and practice of medicine, history of Bukhara, science, faith, medicine, healthcare, personality of the doctor Momindzhan.*

Introduction.

The actuality of research. Special attention is being paid to establishing the Third Renaissance in New Uzbekistan, raising science and intellectual potential in every way, specialists in the field of "Folk medicine" are being trained in the medical universities of our republic, rationally solving the problems faced by modern medicine on the basis of combining the advanced achievements of Eastern medicine and Western medicine. In order to solve this problem, it is important to study the unique knowledge and experiences of our great ancestors, including Mominjon Hakim Margilani, on a scientific basis.

The level of study of the problem. Since the 70s of the last century, interest in Eastern medicine and its unique philosophical outlook has been growing. The reason for this can be explained by the following circumstances: First, the traditions of folk medicine and Eastern philosophy continue to develop continuously in the countries of the Indo-Chinese Peninsula, such as India, China, Korea, and Malaysia, and secondly, they occupy an important place in maintaining the health of the population of these countries. Thirdly, since the second half of the 20th century, the signs of technicism in medical thinking are increasing, and the tendency to separate the patient from the whole person is increasing. On top of that, the newly formed fields of medicine began to insist on the study of individual parts of the human body instead of a whole.

By the 20th century, there were very important changes in scientific thinking, especially in the scientific thinking of medicine. Advances in scientific and technical development have created great opportunities in the diagnosis and treatment of patients. The chemical method of treatment, which began to develop rapidly from the second half of the last century, was undoubtedly a significant contribution to the work of modern treatment. Since 1972, the World Health Organization has paid special attention to the comprehensive promotion of the study of folk medicine and traditional medicine, especially the study of the scientific heritage of Eastern medicine.

In 1975, the Executive Committee of the World Health Organization and in 1977 the World Health Assembly adopted a special resolution to further strengthen research in the field of folk

medicine. In it, it was recommended to further strengthen the research of various areas of the heritage of ancient medicine, which considers it important to understand Eastern medicine as a holistic phenomenon of the past culture (2,8.)

It is known that the idea and ideology that reigned in the conditions of the former Soviet system unilaterally condemned the religious worldview and folk medicine and brutally persecuted doctors and priests. The rich heritage of Eastern medicine has been destroyed. During the years of national independence, special attention was paid to the study of our religious and spiritual values, including the medical heritage of our great ancestors, on a comprehensive scientific basis, and to the harmonization of the advanced achievements of medicine and folk medicine. The publication of the book "I will not stop until I reach you" by researchers: Rahmatullah Fayzullaev and Nodirjon Abdulhatov in understanding and analyzing the essence of the socio-political processes of the peoples of Turkestan, especially in the Bukhara Emirate and the Kokan Khanate, in the end of the 19th century - the beginning of the 20th century, is the history of our country. was a very important event for specialists dealing with the history of medicine and medicine (1).

Also, scientists of Fergana Institute of Public Health: Mahmudov N. I., Sidikov A. In the work "Organization and development of the medical system in the Fergana region" (2) published by A. Tukhtakulov, the medical activities and achievements of Mominjon Hakim Margiloniy (Mominjon Aliev) were researched in the most general way for the first time. When comparing some of the facts in the textbook with the facts presented in "Mo'minjon Hakim Manoqibi", it was noticed that there are conflicting and controversial places.

Research method and result. Scientific objectivity, analysis and synthesis, historicity and logic, comparison, critical approach methods were used in the research process.

Mominjon Hakim Aliev was born in 1894 in the village of Khamrak, near the city of Margylan. He went to a religious school from the age of seven. He attracts the attention of his teachers with his extraordinary sharp mind, strong memory and the height of his passion for learning. He will enjoy their kindness. However, after a year, his mother dies. His period of bitter orphanhood begins, despite his stepmother's opposition to his study in a religious school, he continues his studies thanks to the kindness and intercession of the great scientists of the time. Mominjon, who was interested in science since childhood, studied in Margilan madrasas. Professor Abdurahimbek, who was the imam of the Khamrak mosque, played a particularly important role in his fate. Then, from the age of 14, he studied in religious madrasas of Bukhara. While studying at the madrasa, he began to deeply study the works of Eastern medicine and practiced medicine. His deep knowledge of medicine quickly made Mominjan Hakim Aliev famous among the people.

After treating the son of one of the court officials, Mir Poyon, from a serious illness, Hakim Muminjan had the opportunity to use the rare works in his library, especially the five-volume "Laws of Medicine" by Abu Ali Ibn Sina. Especially after Devonbegi Nasrullahbek appointed him as a palace physician in June 1915, he had the opportunity to use rare metals and minerals kept in the palace treasury: dur (pearl), ruby, turquoise, gold, silver, mummy, and rare metals and minerals to treat serious patients. Mominjon Hakim will get to know the rich heritage of unique Eastern literature stored in the palace library; they become perfect people in all respects.

After Mominjon Hakim became a court physician, the highest-ranking officials began to address him as "Eshoni Hakim".

About this, Mominjon Hakim said: "First the soldiers, then when the people found out, the citizens also started coming for treatment. According to Bukhara custom, they used to meet the healer in the morning at lunch. Patients never come empty-handed, six pieces of warm bread, a kilo of holvo and some of them come with half a kilo of tea. They also give 5-6 coins in return. In the evening, without leaving anything, I will distribute it to the students of the madrasa. Now nobody calls my name Abdulmomin. A new famous name appeared among the people, everyone began to address him as "Eshoni hakim" (1, 248). Mominjon Hakim, while explaining the main reasons why he was known as a court physician in Bukhara and large cities, quotes the wise saying of Sheikh Saadi: "For every fault, the king is pisandad - hunarast", that is, if one fault of a person is acceptable to the king, it will be replaced by craft (skill, art): "If for some reason a person becomes popular with corruptors and kings, he immediately becomes acceptable to the people" (1, 256). This law was repeated in the case of Mominjon Hakim even during the years of Soviet power.

The great Sufis have so many prophesied that disaster follows fame. About this, Eshoni Hakim wrote: "Some people did not like me to be famous. I secretly practiced medicine until 1915. My room in the Shodibek madrasa was convenient for my secret work. There were three shelves in the room, each of which was a wooden shelf. I used to keep my medical books and necessary equipment and medicines secret on these shelves. If I gave medicine to anyone, I would say that I got it from the judges" (1, 257-258).

Mominjon Hakim emphasized that intuition played a very important role in the treatment of seriously ill patients. He considered the true dreams seen in sleep to be a secret secret beyond the understanding of the human mind: if they asked me with what evidence you say that, I had no evidence except from the inspiration of my heart" (1, 249).

Malaria, rabies, pulmonary tuberculosis and other infectious diseases were widespread in Bukhara and surrounding villages, and these were drying the pillow of the common people. Malaria was called "swamp fever". Hakim Mominjon often preached that malaria is contagious, that it is spread by mosquitoes in the swamps, and that swamps should be drained to eliminate this disease. Rishta disease was also common among the population of Bukhara. A 20-50 cm worm was coming out of the wound, creating a purulent wound under the patient's skin. Sometimes the length of this worm was up to 90 cm. Hakim Mominjon from Margilan took an active part in the fight against malaria and rabies in Bukhara. After the dissolution of the Bukhara Emirate, Mominjan Hakim Aliev entered the medical faculty of the Central Asian State University. This faculty is separated as Samarkand State Medical Institute. After Mominjon Hakim Aliev graduated from the institute with "excellent" grades in 1935, he gained a great reputation among his colleagues and specialists, not only as a brilliant scholar of Oriental medicine, but also as a highly educated doctor who achieved positive results in the use of Eastern medicine and the advanced achievements of Western medicine in medical practice. . He first worked as a doctor-surgeon in Fergana, then in Yalta spas. For a quarter of a century, he worked as the chief physician of the "Uzbekistan" sanatorium in Sochi.

These years were the years of creating innovations in his life and work, revitalizing scientific research. (3,91)

Mominjon Hakim Margiloni worked on his candidate's thesis on the topic "Effect of eucalyptus plant on the patient's organism". Finally, as a product of many years of research, the dissertation was successfully defended at the Scientific Council of the Moscow State Medical Institute. By the decision of the specialized scientific council at the Moscow Medical Institute,

Mominjon Aliev was awarded the degree of candidate of medical sciences. Mominjon Hakim Aliev was the first medical scientist to come out of Margylan, and he was the author of Eucalyptus tincture. This drug was very helpful to patients in the treatment of inflammatory diseases of the upper respiratory tract. Mominjan Hakim was a versatile and talented medical scientist. He could write and talk fluently in Russian, Armenian, Azerbaijani, Persian, Turkish, Arabic, English. (3.92).

Mominjon Hakim Margilani, thinking about his hard-working, but in many ways exemplary life, the main factor of his achievements throughout his life, he said that he was under the control of Allah since childhood, his endless love and devotion to knowledge, and that he made his whole body and existence useful for people, not the world rich from Allah. he specifically emphasized that he asked for it, and that he did not fall prey to transient and deceptive worldly wealth, actions and titles. "When I look at my other colleagues, I never find what I want in them. Their outlook is different, their intentions are completely different. A world full of goals. And I had no other goal than to do good to people. Humanity is the main criterion for me, and I look for that from whoever they are. If I find such a person, he will be considered a good person for me. ... My hope for those who read these memoirs is that they live in the world striving for a goal. Because the goal is undoubtedly to bring a person to high positions. Those who say they will reach their goal without patience are mistaken," he wrote (1, 469, 470-471).

Conclusion: Mominjon Hakim Aliev knew our history well and was an allama who loved literature. The unique and truthful facts presented by him in this review serve as an important source for the truthful coverage of the history of our country on a scientific basis, removing the one-sidedness and forgeries related to the history of the Bukhara Emirate during the former Soviet regime.

Mominjon Hakim Margilani was a scholar with a broad encyclopedic worldview, a talented poet, a clever and intelligent thinker, a good physician and a great person whose worldview is written in capital letters. Every reader with a pure heart who reads *Manoqib* will be sure of this, admire it, be proud of it and aspire to it.

The scientific, historical, artistic, religious and moral works of Mominjon Hakim Margilani, rich in philosophical observations, undoubtedly serve as an important source in educating young people in the spirit of high moral ideals, patriotism, enlightenment, and progress.

REFERENCES

1. Раҳматуллоҳ Файзуллаев, Нодиржон Абдулаҳадов. Сенга етмагунча тўхтамайман (Мўминжон Ҳаким маноқиб). VII. – Т.: “NOSHIR”, 2022. 476 б.
2. Рўзматзода Қ. Р., Мамадалиев Н. Қ., Эгамназаров А. И. Халқ таобати фалсафаси. Медицина олий ўқув юртлари “Халқ таобати” йўналиши талабалари учун ўқув қўлланма. Фарғона, Classic, 2022. – 215 б.
3. Маҳмудов Н. И., Сидиков А.А., Тухтакулов А.Ю. Фарғона вилоятида тиббиёт тизимининг ташкил топиши ва ривожланиши. Медицина олий ўқув юртлари талабалари учун ўқув қўлланма. – Фарғона, Classic, 2023. -210 б.